

EXTRACURRICULAR FORMS OF WORK ON THE STUDY OF POETIC HERITAGE A.S. PUSHKIN

Abdullayev Shahriyor Otabek O'g'li
Raxmatov Amir Ravshanovich

2 th year students

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute named after Mukimiy
Uzbekistan, Kokand.
Scientific consultant

Ayupov Timur Rustamovich.

Senior Lecturer, Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
named after Mukimiy,
Uzbekistan, Kokand.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10690849>

ANNOTATION

Both developmental learning and problem-based teaching, individualization and differentiation of learning and intensification of the educational process will not be effective without the development of firmly formed interests of students. One of the ways to develop interest in literature and art is to organize the educational process in such a way that it constitutes an organic unity of classroom and extracurricular work and represents an integral system.

A necessary condition for accomplishing the task, developing literary and artistic interests and deepening the literary knowledge of students is the connection of extracurricular work with the curriculum, the systematic and regular conduct of extracurricular work, the variety of its forms, the mass participation of schoolchildren in it, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students.

Key words: *Comments, creativity, changes, analysis, A.S. Pushkin, M.D. Kocherin, G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, OK. Bogomolov.*

The systematic use of various forms of extracurricular work creates conditions for deepening knowledge on issues and problems of interest to students. In the classroom, situations are created that confront students with the need to expand their horizons. They should stimulate the desire to engage in extracurricular and non-school institutions, hobby groups. In turn, extracurricular activities should give rise to schoolchildren's need to implement their knowledge in the classroom. Such a connection between classroom and extracurricular activities will contribute to the activation of the entire educational process. [1. p. 8-9]

One of the signs of consistency in the organization of extracurricular activities is the implementation of interdisciplinary connections. So, for example, realizing the connections between literature and the Russian language, the work of a literary circle is organized, focusing on the language of the work. This contributed to the understanding of the artistic image in its literary and linguistic embodiment, allowing the circle members to feel the expressiveness, flexibility and ambiguity of the Russian language. As a result of the activities of the literary and language circle, the activity of its participants in the lessons increased: they had three times more grades in these subjects compared to other students and a higher quality of creative works and essays.

Based on the systematic use of interdisciplinary connections, it is possible to organize and conduct complex extracurricular activities, for example, the 9th grade evening “Music salons of the 19th century”, based on the combination of the study of the poetic creativity of A.S. Pushkin and musical art of the 19th century. Preparation for the evening includes organizing a school exhibition, thematic focus of the work of school clubs, and conducting an excursion to the local history museum. [1. p. 181]

The system of extracurricular activities promotes the possibility of transferring students' interests to new areas of art.

When studying the poetic heritage of Pushkin, it is possible to use a variety of forms of extracurricular work: excursions, evenings, debates, exhibitions, clubs, extracurricular activities, etc. And at the same time, we note that extracurricular work on literature is effective and efficient when its forms are interconnected and constitute with all their diversity, unity, when, interpenetrating and complementing each other, they are mobile and harmonious, that is, when it is a system. Each form of extracurricular work is a separate link in a single chain. Thus, a literary excursion can precede a literary evening, which, in turn, will require preparation of a literary exhibition or debate. At the same time, each form of extracurricular work is independent and autonomous. [2. p. 101]

Clubs are the most common and stable form of extracurricular work in literature. They allow students to deepen their knowledge and develop interest in literature and art through excursions, literary exhibitions, electives, and evenings.

One of the most effective forms of extracurricular activities is literary evenings. Closely related to educational work, they contribute to the generalization of the range of knowledge in art, history and other subjects

related to literature. In the process of preparing and conducting literary evenings, students have the opportunity to develop the necessary skills in working with books, reference literature, selecting and organizing material.

What happens to the student with such a systematic approach to organizing extracurricular activities? First of all, the process of perceiving artistic phenomena is activated, it becomes more focused and accurate. This movement of the reader forward. [3. p. 11]

In extracurricular activities, a variety of tasks can be solved: analysis of a specific work, familiarization with the facts of cultural life, entry into the world of other, previously little known or completely unfamiliar artistic phenomena, etc. There is another task that can be successfully solved through extracurricular activities - the integration of individual information in the minds of students, the formation of a holistic picture, for example, about a certain era. It is impossible to truly understand and feel Pushkin's heroes, the atmosphere of the life they live, and, finally, to understand and feel the poet himself without imagining the specific realities of life that filled Pushkin's era. An example of an extracurricular event that solves this problem would be the "Literary Lounge".

An appeal to various kinds of sources (pedagogical, methodological) showed that the development of a unified system of classroom and extracurricular activities is one of the pressing problems of methodological science and school practice. Researchers substantiate systems of principles, types, forms, methods of activity of students and teachers in the process of extracurricular work. Such a system, in our opinion, is necessary when studying the work of any poet and writer, but when studying the poetic heritage of A.S. Pushkin - especially, since he is the greatest Russian poet, whose work is necessary for children at any age and in any class to become familiar with. [4. p. 94]

A literary text, including poetic text, is the material on which the reader's dialogue with the author and his cultural era is built, it is a means of penetration into another culture with its system of universal values and worldview. Dialogical study of literary works is an effective means of activating students' ways of thinking, developing independent thinking, and the foundations of research activity.

In our article we tried to understand the essence of this problem and highlight the use of dialogue of arts in literature lessons for the study of the lyrics of A.S. Pushkin.

Also in our work, we tried to trace how extracurricular work can be organized at school to study the poetic heritage of a poet, and came to the conclusion that it can be implemented in various forms: electives, clubs, creative evenings.

Practice shows that clubs are the most common and stable form of extracurricular work in literature. They allow students to deepen their knowledge and develop interest in literature and art through excursions, literary exhibitions, electives, and evenings.

One of the most effective forms of extracurricular activities is literary evenings. Closely related to educational work, they contribute to the generalization of the range of knowledge in art, history and other subjects related to literature. In the process of preparing and conducting literary evenings, students have the opportunity to develop the necessary skills in working with books, reference literature, and learn to select and systematize material. The range of knowledge of students who took part in extracurricular activities expands significantly. They compare works of painting, the work of artists with similar works and phenomena in literature. A great literary and artistic awareness of the participants in extracurricular activities and the breadth of their artistic interests are revealed. They were able to compare the works of two or more. The literary lounge allows you to involve almost all students in the work. Moreover, the "action" itself is the result of a lot of preparatory work, during which schoolchildren accumulate knowledge by communicating through art.

The specifics of the school subject of literature, according to G.A. Gukovsky, is that "at school we study both art itself and the science of it." Indeed, in literature, as an educational subject, two forms of cognition are combined - figurative (artistic) and logical (scientific). [5. p. 71-74]

But figurative cognition is impossible without the emotional sphere. As literary critic V.V. aptly notes. Fedorov: "The poetic world, in addition to the characters' actions depicted in words and perceived, includes such actions, the object of which is the reader. The emotion experienced by the reader, being an event of his completely personal - spiritual life, is at the same time an event of the works. Therefore, when talking about an active approach to teaching literature, we must take into account the emotional impact of the work, the emotional response of the reader.

A real opportunity to implement the conditions and requirements set out above is a system of classroom and extracurricular work to study Pushkin's creative

heritage at school, correlated with the educational process. This will allow students to purposefully and systematically form and develop literary and artistic skills as the basis for increasing the aesthetic level of comprehension of a work,” as well as “systematically and systematically accumulate creative experience.”

Bibliography:

1. Belenky G.I. Theory of literature in secondary school. – M.: Education, 2016.
2. Bogomolova L.K. Commented reading of the first chapters of the novel by A.S. Pushkin “Eugene Onegin” // In the collection: Scientific notes of the Leningrad State. Pedagogical Institute named after A.M. Herzen. – L., 2017.
3. Bocharov G.K. A system of lessons for studying A.S. Pushkin’s story “The Captain’s Daughter.” – M.: Education, 2022.
4. Lakhotsky K.P., Frolova V.F. Pushkin at school. – M., 2016. – P. 361 – 404.
5. Pressman L.P. Extracurricular work on literature. M.: Education, 2013.

